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Marriage and family in Polish law. Selected aspects

According to Article 18 of the Constitution of the Republic of Poland, marriage as a union of a woman and a man, family, motherhood, and parenthood are under the protection and care of the Republic of Poland.

Motherhood signifies a special bond between a mother and her child, primarily arising from the biological conditions of a woman's body. It also encompasses the period of pregnancy, thus lasting both before and after the birth of the child. Parenthood, as a constitutional term, has been introduced into Article 18 primarily to ensure that the role of the father is not constitutionally overlooked. Parenthood therefore refers to both the mother and the father. It encompasses the autonomy of parents to make decisions regarding procreation and serves as the foundation for parental authority.

The obligation to protect specified in Article 18 of the Constitution of the Republic of Poland primarily means that public authorities must take actions to prevent threats to marriage, family, motherhood, and parenthood.

Pursuant to Article 23 of the Family and Guardianship Code, spouses have equal rights and responsibilities in marriage. They are obliged to common cohabitation, to provide mutual assistance and fidelity, and to cooperate for the benefit of the family they have established through their union. The content of Article 23 of the Family and Guardianship Code is a transposition of the provisions regarding the protection of marriage and family contained in the Constitution of the Republic of Poland, including Article 18.

According to the judgement of the Supreme Court of 22 October 1999: "Common cohabitation within the meaning of Article 23 of the Code of Family and Guardianship Law consists of the spiritual, physical, and economic bond of spouses, which is the purpose of marriage and enables the realization of its fundamental tasks."

Cooperation for the benefit of the family referred to in Article 23 is an obligation of a maintenance nature. It means the spouse's involvement in the actions of the other spouse and providing them with support – emotional, organizational, and physical – in every

situation.

The obligation of mutual assistance between spouses specified in Article 23 is closely linked to the duty of cooperation for the good of the family, which encompasses all actions necessary for the proper functioning of the family, including the appropriate upbringing of children and refraining from behaviors that could harm the interests of the family as a whole and its individual members.

Pursuant to Article 24 of the Family and Guardianship Code, spouses jointly decide on important family matters; in the absence of agreement, either of them may seek a court resolution.

In Article 24 of the Family and Guardianship Code, there is mention of "important family matters"; this provision refers to all issues, including property matters. Important family matters include, for example, determining the child's place of residence, establishing the spouse's place of residence, or determining the allocation of earned income. Important family matters can also include disputes between spouses regarding the maintenance of an equal standard of living for family members. It should be noted that some of these disputes are resolved by the court based on other provisions.

References:

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